

Institutional Support for Online Discussion Forum Use in Nigerian Polytechnics

Lateef Alhaji Bello (CLN)

Department of Library and Information Science, Federal Polytechnic, Offa, Nigeria
babdullateef62@gmail.com

Saheed Abiola Hamzat (PhD)

Department of Library and Information Science, Adeleke University, Nigeria
saheed.abiola@adelekeuniversity.edu.ng

Ibidapo Oketunji (Professor)

Department of Library and Information Science, Adeleke University, Nigeria
ibidapo.oketunji@adelekeuniversity.edu.ng
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Abstract

Online discussion forum (ODF) as an effective pedagogical tool for learning and knowledge construction, designed to make the learning process robust and all-encompassing. It is also expected to facilitate faster and smooth access to learning aid and for individualisation of learning. In spite of its enormous benefits, previous studies have shown that students do not make use of ODF as expected due to factors largely attributed to low level of awareness and perception without recourse to the role of institutional support. Institutional support is expected to motivate the students to be highly engaged in their learning process, this study, therefore, investigated institutional support for ODF use among Library and Information Science (LIS) students in selected Nigeria Polytechnics. Technology Organisation Environment Theory (TOE) (Fleischer, 1990), Media System Dependency (MSD) (Ball-Rokeach and Defleur, 1976) and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989) provided the framework, while the descriptive survey design of correlational type was used. The population comprised all ND II LIS students in eight Nigerian polytechnics offering LIS as a course. Six hundred and thirteen (613) students were enumerated in the eight polytechnics in Southwestern, Nigeria. The instrument used were ODF ($\alpha = 0.87$), Institutional support ($\alpha = 0.91$). Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The majority of the respondents were males (53.4%) while most of the students were found within the age brackets of 21-25 years (44.6%) with a mean age of 22.8+/-1.05. Google Answers Box (\bar{x} = 1.86) and Experts-Exchange (\bar{x} = 1.52) were the mostly used ODF by the students but with low frequency of use (\bar{x} = 2.48). Further, Institutional supports provided were moderate, technical support (\bar{x} = 2.84) and low Infrastructure (\bar{x} = 2.47). Institutional support is an influencer of online discussion forum use among LIS students in polytechnics. Government and polytechnic authorities should take cognisance of these factors particularly institutional use for optimal and efficient use of ODF.

Keywords: Online Discussion Forum, Institutional support, LIS students, Nigeria, Polytechnics

Introduction

The use of educational technologies is expected to increase accessibility to learning resources and facilitate multiple learning approaches for diverse learners. A manifestation of technology usage in education is the Online Discussion Forum (ODF) which provides both synchronous and asynchronous interactions for learners. Online Discussion Forum is an electronic platform for online learning, discussion, knowledge sharing, and information dissemination. Online discussion forum is a web-based application that brings users with shared interest and mind-set together. Members of the ODF have the privilege to post messages to the discussion threads, interact and receive feedback from other students and instructors, and hence create a deeper understanding of the subject matter being discussed (Alabo & Emmah, 2018). Online discussion forum is an important knowledge-exchanging pattern and teaching method that provides learning opportunities with no temporal and geographic barriers (Nandi et al., 2015). This web-based online platform provides a virtual space for learners to engage in social interactions and at the same time, post ideas, discuss and debate with others. Online discussion forum is widely considered as an example of new technologies being used in a blended educational environment to supplement traditional face-to-face teaching and learning methods (Cheng et al., 2016).

Online discussion forum takes teaching and learning beyond a confined learning environment through flexibility and convenience. Students drive the learning process in online forum, and more emphasis is placed on knowledge sharing than lesson notes. It could be stated that the popularity of online discussion forum as a tool for teaching and learning keep growing, due to the flexibility of responding to messages and posts at user's preferred times. Online discussion forum plays an important role in tertiary education through elimination of communication barriers between students and teachers (Xiaoling, 2018). It also provides avenue for fruitful discussions among students and peers. Balaji and Diganta (2016) surmised that the use of online discussion forum has emerged as an effective tool for engaging students outside the classroom. It allows students to post messages to the discussion threads, interact and receive feedback from colleagues and instructors, and foster deeper understanding towards the subject under study. An online forum creates a motivational environment for free expression of views and ideas with more confidence than in a traditional classroom. The introvert (shy) learners can easily improve their involvement in the teaching and learning process via online discussion forum, as they feel more comfortable to share opinions from any location without much pressure (Zuheir et al., 2017).

A number of factors have been identified to influence the use of Online Discussion Forum among learners in higher institutions of learning. Prominent among these are institutional support, ICT competence and social influence. However, the institution support constitutes the focal point of this study. Institutional support refers to the resources, opportunities, privileges, and services which institutions transmit to students (Stanton-Salazar, 2017). The supports include technical support, infrastructure facilities, implemented policies, financial support among others. It has been affirmed that institutional factors provide an important background and good platform for the participation of students especially the Library and Information Science (LIS) students (Li & Atuahene-Gima, 2018). Institutional support plays important roles in influencing students such as LIS students' innovation behaviours in terms of accessing the resources and responding to various questions asked by tutors in teaching and learning process especially in online discussion forum (Guo, 2017).

An example of institutional supports is Technical support which refers to the specialised skill provided by management to support and assist students in the use of technology for learning. Meanwhile, Dexter et al. (2016) have characterised the technical support as the access, operation and troubleshooting of hardware, software and network resources. According to Frost and Sullivan (2017), technical support includes ICT facilities, vendor and internal helpdesks provided within the educational setting. Technical support has an encouraging impact on students' use of ICT and active participation in online discussion forum as well as their integration of ICT into teaching-learning processes (Moses et al., 2018). For this reason, it is essential to provide guidance, support and services as parts of the technology applications for LIS students to participate fully in online discussion forum.

Literature review

Communication and participation are two crucial determinants in the quality of teaching and learning (Durairaj & Umar, 2015). One of the drivers in the increasing utilisation of the Internet for teaching and learning is the way text communications enable users to interact more deeply with live information. Online education thus widens the ways in which adaptable, suitable and collaborative instructional techniques make it possible to share ideas, make inquiries and present individual discoveries as they happen, and at the convenience of the users (Taye, 2016). One element in computer-mediated communication has been the evolution of the online discussion forum, which is a web-based application widely used to bring together individuals with a shared interest, making it a useful tool for facilitating communication in large student classes. The benefits provided include effective consultation and collaboration between instructors and students, and among the students themselves (Biriya & Emmah, 2015; Haris et al., 2017).

One of the most appealing features of online discussion forum is that it provides opportunities for students to take ownership of their own learning, and spur them to easily create or construct knowledge. Learners can easily link up with other learners online leading to exchange of learning materials, ideas and skills in related areas. It has become a tool for implementation of technology usage in education. Many educational institutions have realised the growing benefits of online discussion to the extent that some are beginning to make it mandatory for students and teachers to participate in e-learning platforms in the school as a way to improve digital literacy skills (Neil & Maria, 2017).

The use of online discussion forum (ODF) has emerged as a common tool and an effective way of engaging students outside the classroom (Balaji & Charkrabarti, 2016). ODF as an e-learning platform that provides students with privilege to post messages to the discussion threads, interact and receive feedback from other students and instructor. Hence, creates a deeper understanding of the subject matter being discussed. In education, ODF have been deployed to complement traditional learning techniques such as lectures and tutorials (Dube, et al., 2016). Online discussion forum harmonises with the educational philosophy that makes communication a necessary tool and fundamental mechanism for effective learning. It was discovered that the interaction of the learners with both human and inanimate objects were essential for the quality of their learning experience. It can enrich the process of knowledge exchange among participants and has positive effects on the students' performance. Consequently, online discussion forum can be successful in enhancing collaborative learning by attracting students to participate and interact (Harman & Koohang, 2015).

DeNoyelles et al. (2014) stated that students participate in forum whenever it suits them and this serves as a strong advantage for those who think of signing up for an online module. Online discussion forums enable asynchronous communication that supports social interaction and teamwork without confining learners to set communication times in the way that online chats do. Haris et al. (2014) define asynchronous online communication as "a text-based human-to-human communication via computer networks that provides a platform for the participants to interact with one another to exchange ideas, insights and personal experiences." According to Durairaj and Umar (2015), social and cognitive development is rooted in social interactions among participants in the learning context of the online discussion forum. These interactions facilitate the movement, exchange and joint creation of knowledge, and also the sharing of experiences in instructor-learner and learner-learner relationships. To Alzahrani (2017), the sharing of online discussion forum experiences indicates that social interactions in the online discussion forum, where theoretical course content is linked to events that occur in the real world, bring about improved learner engagement and learning outcomes while also ensuring continuous interactivity between students and lecturers. Social interaction between students and instructors in an asynchronous online forum and with the content that features in the forum has the capacity to enhance individual learning experiences beyond surface learning and take it to a level of applying content to real-world cases (deeper level), and of creating new knowledge (Durairaj & Umar, 2015).

According to Wei et al. (2015), increased interactivity nurtured by the online discussion forum stimulates deep learning by actively engaging students in the learning process. This deep learning, facilitated in the online discussion forum, happens when the student actively searches for and finds information, utilises it to create knowledge, and integrates the information for his or her own cognitive development (Redmond et al., 2014). Online discussion forums offer a useful way to engage with course content and create knowledge via extended dialogue (Redmond et al., 2014). Consequently, deep and meaningful learning through social interactions was experienced in every situation where one of the three forms of interaction is present: student to instructor, student to student, or student with content (Durairaj & Umar, 2015).

Thor et al. (2017) indicated that an online discussion forum is less intimidating for students who are reluctant to speak in lectures as it is less likely to be dominated by participants who are

outspoken in face-to-face contexts. The virtual context of the online discussion forum has greater benefits for less assertive students than for extrovert students as it offers all participants extended time to think about and respond to others' inputs (Kent et al., 2016). The communication between participants of this kind of forum for student-lecturer interaction presents more conducive student participation, since individuals can make known their opinions on an issue of learning without being shy or intimidated by the presence of others (Biriya & Emmah, 2014).

For Haris et al. (2014), this confirms that asynchronous online discussion can be of immense advantage to students who find it difficult to participate in face-to-face lectures because they lack confidence. Alzahrani (2017) stressed that the online discussion forum encourages students to work together and share learning experiences as they learn from each other through social interaction in the forum. Examples of online discussion forum include: Google answers box, reddit, askubuntu, quora, experts-exchange among others.

Online forum does not only promote learning interest but also accommodate different categories of learners including those with special needs who may find it difficult to be physically present at the traditional classroom all the time or to keep pace with other learners in the class. It also enhances inclusive learning - enabling individuals to learn at their own pace and time, and to freely contribute to discussions on the platform (Khe et al., 2018). Jeff (2019) stated that with online discussion forum, everyone has ample opportunities to be heard, and connected with other classmates, ensuring equity among all voices in classroom, and less intimidation for introverted students. From the aforementioned benefits, it is obvious that online discussion forum has enormous potentials to motivate students learning interest, activate participation, and student-teacher communication. It also has the potential to increase student's sophistication in use of digital learning platforms, and formulation of new topics or ideas for discussion and research.

Students' participation also has positive effects on students' learning and performances. Thus, instructors need to explore ways to strengthen students' engagement and involvement as a matter of importance. The scholars stress further that it is necessary to keep on examining the factors promoting or hindering the effectiveness of technology since its roles are increasing in education. More so, the knowledge of how students learn can be beneficial to both instructors and students. It is also necessary to identify the perceived usefulness that can help develop strategies for enhancing students' learning experiences and academic performances in e-learning. In the same vein, it is germane to have an understanding of what promotes students' engagement in online discussions (Lee & Martin, 2017).

Institutional support is a general reflection of financial and technical support from the institution management and its agencies, which provide lecturers and students with critical resources that they may use for teaching and learning (Sheng et al., 2013; Shu et al., 2015). Support from the government and its agencies allows organisation to interpret policies and programme correctly, and thus, decreasing environmental uncertainty (Ma et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2015). Researchers argue that institutional support plays an important role in the use of online discussion forum by lecturers and students (Guo et al., 2016). Ivancevich (2014) holds that institutional support is a number of support and feelings received by colleagues, superiors, and departments that assist in the success of tasks and work. Erdogan and Enders (2017) affirmed that institutional support is an individual's belief that organisations care and provide input by providing assistance and support. According to Mathis and Jackson (2018) institutional support is the assistance/motivation received from the parent organisation in the form of training, equipment, expectations and productive work teams, while Ratna (2018) focuses on institutional support for an institution of learning, namely the extent to which universities provide support, assistance when needed, appreciation of contributions, care for social-emotional needs, well-being, relationships and feelings of mutual assistance among lecturers and leader.

The institutional support in this context refers to the organisational active encouragement in form of policies, regulations, monetary and non-monetary help that propel employees to perform

their responsibilities in a very effective and productive manner. Any organisation including the institutions of higher learning that is willing to earn employees commitment must be ready to give adequate support. For instance, some of the institutional supports that can be provided by institutions of higher learning include: research support in form of conference sponsorship, research grants, publication support; technical support as well as pedagogical support particularly in a knowledge-based economy (Al-Enazi, 2016). Institutional support consists of a set of physical facilities, software or processes, made available by the organisation, which make learning success possible. It is addressed to all agents involved: managers, tutors, student teachers, and administrative staff among others. Some examples: to allow interaction between students and teachers and with other students there may be learning management systems; to allow management of administrative aspects there may be electronic office services, to optimise the use of technology throughout the organisation, technical support.

Reddy (2021) also described the term institutional support as part of economic environment of industry and business. It consists of authorities and institutions whose decisions and active support in form of laws, regulation, financial and non-financial help brings a lot of changes in the functioning of any business. The institutional support includes funding, training, motivation, granting of fringe benefits among others. Funding of training programmes for students such as workshop, seminar, and granting of fringe benefits should be considered and encouraged. Most Nigerian polytechnics are underfunded and treated with disdain without adequate recognition; while undermining that all accreditation exercise and earned allowances are not approved. Such negative trend is possible to ginger young and promising librarians to move to a more suitable and well-paid job in other professions. For such trend to be reversed, older professionals ought to stand their ground and endeavour to be heard in the comity of professionals and academics.

According to Oxford English Dictionary (OED), infrastructure which is another indicator of Institutional Support is described as the basic foundations of society or enterprise. Academic infrastructure refers to the hardware or equipment, software applications and services associated with ICTs, including the network infrastructure, the computing infrastructure, the system and application software, the Internet Service Provider (ISP), the bandwidth, the policy framework and the security infrastructure. Murali (2009) rightly stressed that learning mode requires a structured network at all its operational nodes and interconnected to each other, through a dedicated network so that all student services can be easily accessed by all operational nodes.

Ehiametalor (2001) described infrastructure as the operational inputs of every instructional programme and constitutes elements that are necessary for teaching and learning. Such include buildings, laboratories, machinery, furniture and electrical fixtures. These must be functional in relation to other aspects of the community, such as health centres, libraries, and good roads and must be large enough to allow for expansion as enrolments expand. In the same vein, Osagie (2003) opines that infrastructure represents the aesthetic picture of the school conveyed by the position of structures in relation to one another. It also represents the empirical relevance of the totality of the school environment for the realisation of the school business (teaching/learning). Osagie asserted in specific terms that school plant is made up of landscape, trees, lawns, hedges, and accompanying paths, playgrounds, buildings, security facilities and utilities. However, a well-equipped and well-maintained physical plant can make learning a more pleasant experience and discourage early drop-outs. It can as well attract better quality teachers. In summary therefore, infrastructure can be viewed as the totality of all that goes into education such as classrooms, lecture theatres, laboratories, libraries, electricity, water, health centre, sports and recreation centres, ICT, machines and furniture put there-in, with the intention of facilitating teaching-learning.

Uche et al. (2011) noted that the physical infrastructures contribute directly or remotely to the teaching and learning process in the educational system. Similarly, Ekundayo (2010) stressed that educational infrastructural facilities are those things which enable a skillful lecturer to achieve a level of instructional effectiveness that far exceeds what is possible when they are not provided.

Adedipe (2007) described carrying capacity as the maximum number of students that a university can sustain for quality education based on its human and material resources. Therefore, infrastructure is among the important operational inputs into any instructional programme. It constitutes elements that are necessary for teaching and learning; and is vital in the development of qualitative university education. Ejiogu (1997) noted four important factors in an attempt to balance the qualitative and quantitative growth of the education system in Nigeria. These range from the quality and number of infrastructure (in forms of buildings, machinery and equipment) through the usage to maintenance of the infrastructure. Okebukola (2005) pointed out that the stress put on the universities in terms of demand and the limited expansion in physical facilities and academic staff to cater for this demand has taken a great toll on the quality of programmes in the institutions.

Subair (2011) thus submitted that the quality of output (graduates) is a function of infrastructure that determines the students' learning environment and their motivation to learn. Quality assurance of the institutional facilities can only be guaranteed if basic conditions and guidelines are followed from the onset. Basically, this means that infrastructural development must make provision for adaptability or alteration probability, flexibility in user demands, accessibility to students, staff and society and due regards for aesthetic and clean environment. Salis (2002) developed a quality indicator checklist which shows what the physical environment and facilities in higher educational institutions must require both in qualitative and quantitative terms. These include availability of infrastructural development programmes (facility provision), adequacy of the facilities in terms of currency and relevance to purpose; students friendliness and centeredness of the facilities (attractive to students and suitable for their needs); regular maintenance and renewal of the dilapidated ones; the infrastructural development must be of international standard (globally acceptable) to attract foreign students, staff and recognition; and must be environmentally safe and of high sanitary standard.

As said earlier and evident from the above previous reviewed studies on the influence of institutional support on online discussion forum use is lacking selected Nigerian Polytechnics context. In the light of this, the current study will:

1. identify the various types of online discussion forum available to LIS students in selected Nigerian polytechnics;
2. ascertain the institutional support provided for LIS students to use online discussion forum in selected Nigerian polytechnics.

Methodology

Design and method

The study adopts survey design whose purpose is to describe the relevant aspects of the phenomena of interest. The survey research design is appropriate for this study because it provides an accurate and valid representation of how institutional support influence online discussion forum use by LIS students in selected Nigerian polytechnics.

Population and sample

There were nineteen (19) polytechnics in South-western Nigeria but only eight were offering Library and Information Science as a course. The population of the study consists of all the National Diploma (ND) II LIS students in the eight polytechnics in South-western Nigeria. The eight polytechnics are: The Federal Polytechnic Ede, Osun State, Federal Polytechnic Ilaro, Ogun State, Yaba College of Technology, Lagos State, The Polytechnic Ibadan, Oyo State, Osun State College of Technology, Esa Oke, Osun State, Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo, Ondo State, The Ibarapa Polytechnic, Oyo State, and Oyo State College of Agriculture, Igbo-Ora, Oyo State. The choice of the National Diploma (ND) II is because of their experience over the newly admitted ND I students and most of the institutions under study do not have Higher National Diploma (HND) programme in Library and Information Science. The preliminary investigation conducted by the researcher showed that there are six hundred and thirteen (613) ND II LIS students across the eight

polytechnics as at February, 2023. The breakdown of the LIS students in the polytechnics is as presented in Table below:

Table 1: Population of ND II LIS students in the eight polytechnics in South-western Nigeria

S/N	Name of Institutions	State	Owner	Number of LIS Students	Level
1.	Federal Polytechnic Ede	Osun	Federal	80	NDII
2.	Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro	Ogun	Federal	60	NDII
3.	Osun State College of Technology, Esa-Oke	Osun	State	70	NDII
4.	Oyo State College of Agriculture and Technology, Igbo-Ora,	Oyo	State	80	NDII
5.	Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo	Ondo	State	70	NDII
6.	Adeseun Ogundoyin Polytechnic, Eruwa	Oyo	State	88	NDII
7.	The Polytechnic, Ibadan	Oyo	State	85	NDII
8.	Yaba College of Technology, Lagos	Lagos	Federal	80	NDII
Total				613	

Source: Office of the academic planning at various polytechnics, 2023

Total enumeration technique was employed to cover all the 613 ND II LIS students in the eight polytechnics in South-western Nigeria due to the manageable size.

Instrument

The instrument that was used for data collection in this study is the questionnaire. The questionnaire is a combination of self-constructed and adapted from the work of Falola et.al (2020), Tella and Isah (2011), Akinde and Adetimirin (2019), Ghavifekr et al. (2016), Ullah and Khan (2017), Ikemba (2017), and Kowalczyk (2008). This technique is preferred because of the literacy level of the study population. Questionnaire is chosen as an instrument because it is appropriate to cover population that is not too large which comprises LIS students. The questionnaire is an acceptable instrument in non-experimental studies. It is tagged “Influence of Institutional Support on Online Discussion Forum Use Questionnaire (IISODFQ)” and it was administered to LIS students in Polytechnics in South-western Nigeria. The questionnaire is designed under five (5) sub-scales with focus on the variables of the study and harmonised in a single questionnaire. The sections are: A, B, C, D and E.

Section A will elicit demographic information of the respondents. It consists of three (3) items as follows: name of institution, gender and age. It contains open and close ended questions.

Section B: This section will elicit information on types of online discussion forum available to LIS students which is developed by the researcher. This section has two (2) sub-scales. The first sub-scale will measure types of ODF used and it consists of five items with options: Used and Not used. The second sub-scale will also elicit information from LIS students on the frequency of use of online discussion forum using scale adapted from Tella and Isah (2011). It will contain five items with a four-point Likert scale with ranked options: Very Often (VO), Often (O), Occasionally (O) and Never (N) with 4, 3, 2, 1 point scoring accordingly. Respondents are to tick which is applicable to them.

Section C: This section will cover information on institutional support using a standardised scale adapted from Falola et al. (2020), Akinde and Adetimirin (2019). This section has two sub-scales. The first sub-scale will measure technical support and consists of five items. The second sub-scale will measure infrastructure. It will consist of five items. It has a four-point Likert scale with ranked options: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) with 4, 3, 2, 1 point scoring accordingly. Respondents are to tick which is applicable to them.

Validity and reliability

Face validity was used to validate the research instrument. In order to ascertain the face validity of the instrument, it was subjected to the scrutiny and correction by two experts on the field of the subject matter. In order to ascertain the reliability, a pre-test of the instrument was carried out using Federal Polytechnic, Offa, Kwara State, which is outside the scope of the study. The pre-test study of the measuring instrument was carried out by administering thirty copies of the questionnaire to LIS students in the aforementioned polytechnic, since the study focused on LIS students in South-western Nigeria. The reliability of each of the section in the instrument was calculated using Cronbach's alpha coefficient values to determine the internal consistency of the measuring items. The overall reliability of the questionnaire returned an $r=0.85$ which exceed the minimum standard of 0.80 suggested for basic research.

Method of data collection

After the scrutiny and correction, the copies of the questionnaire were administered on the LIS NDII students in the eight polytechnics offering LIS as a course in South-western Nigeria. For effective administration of the questionnaire, three adequately trained Research Assistants was engaged, to complement the researcher's efforts in collecting the data for a period of two weeks. The copies of the questionnaire were administered on LIS students in their respective departments immediately after their Catalogue II lecture which is a compulsory course. This will facilitate early responses, easy and immediate returns and an opportunity to clarify doubt, if any. The respondents were given time to fill in their responses in the questionnaire, after which the completed copies were retrieved and collated for analysis.

Data analysis and results

The data collected for this study was analysed using Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS). Specifically, frequency table, simple percentage, mean and standard deviation was used to measure the research questions. A total of 613 copies of the questionnaire were administered to LIS students in selected Nigerian polytechnics. However, 589 copies were returned but 567 were found usable and valid for analysis, giving a response rate of 92.5%. In addition, the overall return rate of 92.5% used for the study is acceptable in line with the submission of Venitha (2015) that 60% response rate is acceptable standard for most research in the Humanities. The information contained in Table 2 showed that The Polytechnic, Ibadan had the highest number of LIS students 82 (14.5%) who participated in the study. This was followed by LIS students from Adeseun Ogundoyin Polytechnic, Eruwa where 80(14.1%) participated in the study, while LIS students from the Oyo State College of Agriculture and Technology, Igbo-Ora were next in rank in terms of participation in the study with 75 (133.2%). The polytechnic with the lowest number of LIS students' participation in the study was Federal Polytechnic Ilaro 56 (9.9%). This was attributed to the number of LIS students' enrolment in the study population. This means that most of the LIS students in the population of the study participated with at least 10% representation.

Also, Table 2 reveals that the gender distribution shows that male students constituted (53.4%) while female students constituted 46.6%. This implies that there were more male LIS students than their female counterparts in the selected polytechnics in South-west, Nigeria. Additionally, the age distribution of the respondents showed that the majority (44.6%) of the respondents were between 21 and 25 years. This was followed by those between 16 – 20 years (35.4%) while the least category of respondents was those above 31 years of age (5.3%). The mean of their age distribution was 21.37 with standard deviation of 3.26. This means that most of the LIS students in selected polytechnics in South-West, Nigeria were young adults. It was deduced from the results on demographic characteristics of LIS students in selected polytechnics in South-West, Nigeria that the distribution of the respondents used in the study was homogenous and not gender-biased, cut across school ages and representative of the target population as they were able to respond appropriately to the questions raised in the study.

Table 2: Demographic distribution of LIS students in selected polytechnics in South-West Nigeria

Demographic Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Name of Polytechnic		
Federal Polytechnic Ede	73	12.9
Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro	56	9.9
Yaba College of Technology, Lagos	74	13.1
Osun State College of Technology, Esa-Oke	62	10.9
Oyo State College of Agriculture and Technology, Igbo-Ora,	75	13.2
Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo	65	11.5
Adeseun Ogundoyin Polytechnic, Eruwa	80	14.1
The Polytechnic, Ibadan	82	14.5
Gender		
Male	303	53.4
Female	264	46.6
Age (Years)		
16 – 20	201	35.4
21 – 25	253	44.6
26 – 30	83	14.6
31 years and above	30	5.3

Source: Research Field Survey, 2022

Research question one: What are the various types of online discussion forum available for use by LIS students in selected Nigerian Polytechnics?

In order to provide answer to research question one, respondents were asked to indicate the various types of online discussion forum (ODF) available to LIS students in their polytechnics. The result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Type of online discussion forum used by LIS students in selected polytechnics

Types	Used		Not used		\bar{x}	δ	Rank
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%			
Google Answers Box	483	85.2	44	14.8	1.86	0.37	1 st
Experts-Exchange	303	53.4	264	46.6	1.54	0.52	2 nd
Quora	206	36.3	361	63.7	1.44	0.48	3 rd
Ask Ubuntu	249	43.9	318	56.1	1.43	0.50	4 th
Reddit	224	39.5	343	60.5	1.40	0.49	5 th

Key: \bar{x} = Mean; δ = Standard deviation

Decision Rule: If mean is 1.0-1.49 = No; 1.50-2.0 = Yes;

Criterion Mean = 1.5

Answers to research question one is summarised in Table 3. The result revealed that LIS students in the selected polytechnics in South-West, Nigeria used some types of various types of online discussion forum (ODF) as indicated by the overall mean score of 1.53, on a scale of 1-2. Majority of the respondents used Google Answers Box (\bar{x} = 1.86) and Experts-Exchange (\bar{x} = 1.54). On the other hand, online discussion forum less used by majority of the respondents were Reddit (\bar{x} = 1.40), Ask Ubuntu (\bar{x} = 1.43) and Quora (\bar{x} = 1.44). The result suggests that LIS students in selected Nigerian polytechnics regard various types of online discussion forum as needed to be used in their respective polytechnics. The implication of this result is that LIS students in Nigerian polytechnics affirmed that Google Answers Box and Experts-Exchange were the two mostly utilized types of online discussion forum (ODF) available to LIS students in selected

Nigerian Polytechnics. However, online discussion forums such as Quora, Ask Ubuntu and Reddit were least utilised.

Research question two: What are the institutional supports provided to use online discussion forum use among LIS students in selected Nigerian Polytechnics?

The essence of research question three was to ascertain the institutional support provided for LIS students to use online discussion forum in selected Nigerian Polytechnics. In doing this, respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement to institutional support items affecting the use of online discussion forum by LIS students in selected Nigerian polytechnics. The result is presented in Table 3.

Table 4: Institutional supports provided to use online discussion forum among LIS students in selected polytechnics in Nigeria

Item	SA		A		D		SD		\bar{x}	δ
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%		
Technical support										
There is provision of functional helpdesk service for queries	167	29.5	150	26.5	143	25.2	107	18.9	2.78	0.82
The ODF platform is user friendly for students to use	160	28.2	179	31.6	150	26.5	78	13.8	2.79	0.82
There is availability of alternate power supply	220	38.8	201	35.4	97	17.1	49	8.6	3.11	0.90
There is provision for adequate software	198	34.9	208	36.7	95	16.8	76	13.4	2.87	0.90
There is effective policies and regulations in managing and using ODF	152	26.8	132	23.3	206	36.3	77	13.6	2.65	0.97
Weighted									2.84	0.882
Infrastructure										
There is adequate Internet facilities within the campus for the use of students	146	25.7	105	18.5	165	29.1	151	26.6	2.29	0.99
The school library is conducive for me to participate in online discussion forum	212	37.4	222	39.2	101	17.8	32	5.6	2.86	0.88
There is constant power supply within the campus to enable me use online discussion forum	118	20.8	115	20.3	188	33.2	146	25.7	2.18	1.01
There are computer system and accessories to enhance online discussion forum use by students	104	18.3	107	18.9	221	39.0	135	23.8	2.08	0.91
My institution management provides adequate furniture and air conditioner in the library to enhance active participation in online forum	233	41.1	194	34.2	95	16.8	45	7.9	2.93	0.94
Weighted									2.47	0.944
Overall weighted mean									2.65	0.913

Key: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD)

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2022

Decision Rule: 1-1.49 = VL (Very Low), 1.5-2.49 = L (Low), 2.5-3.49 = H (High), while 3.5-4 = VH (Very High). Criterion mean =2.50

Results on the institutional supports provided to use online discussion forum among LIS students in selected Polytechnics in Nigeria as shown in Table 4, revealed that the institutional supports were considered under two indicators namely technical support and infrastructural support. The weighted mean for each indicator was used as the benchmark for the decision. On technical support, majority of the respondents affirmed the provision of adequate software ($\bar{x} = 2.87$), user friendly ODF platform ($\bar{x} = 2.79$) and alternative power supply ($\bar{x} = 3.11$). The weighted mean for

technical support was 2.84 (St.D = 0.891). This means that the level of technical support provided to use online discussion forum among LIS students in selected polytechnics in Nigeria was high since the weighted mean was a little above the criterion mean of 2.5. In other words, the result implies that technical support was adequately provided as institutional support for online discussion forum for LIS students with particular references to the provision of alternative power supply, adequate software and user friendly ODF platforms, among others.

Similarly, the result of infrastructural support for ODF revealed that majority of the respondents indicated a low level of infrastructural provision with a weighted mean of 2.47. Specifically, the respondents affirmed that the school library favourably participates in online discussion forum ($\bar{x} = 2.86$) and that institution management provides adequate furniture and air conditioner in the library to enhance active participation in online forum ($\bar{x} = 2.93$). However, majority of the respondents disagreed that there were adequate Internet facilities within the campus for the use of students ($\bar{x} = 2.29$), constant power supply within the campus to enable me use online discussion forum ($\bar{x} = 2.18$) and computer system and accessories to enhance online discussion forum use by students ($\bar{x} = 2.08$). This implies that the infrastructural support provided for online discussion forum by LIS students in selected Nigerian polytechnics was low especially in the areas of constant power supply within the campus, computer systems and accessories and adequate Internet facilities within the campus for the use of students. Overall, the weighted mean recorded was 2.65 which was a little above the criterion mean, it is therefore concluded that there was a moderate level of institutional support provided to use online discussion forum among LIS students in selected Polytechnics in Nigeria but with a deficit in the level of infrastructural support.

Discussion of finding

Finding of the research question one revealed that LIS students in selected Nigerian polytechnics regard various types of online discussion forum as needed to be used in their respective polytechnics. The implication of this result is that LIS students in Nigerian polytechnics affirmed that Google Answers Box and Experts-Exchange were the two mostly utilised types of online discussion forum (ODF) available to LIS students in selected Nigerian Polytechnics. However, online discussion forums such as Quora, Ask Ubuntu and Reddit were least utilised. It was inferred from this finding that the use of online discussion forum is gradually being accepted by LIS students in Nigerian polytechnics. This finding partly agrees with Balaji and Charkrabarti (2016) that the use of online discussion forum (ODF) has emerged as a common tool and an effective way of engaging students outside the classroom.

Similarly, the finding aligns with that of Neil and Maria, (2017) who asserted that many educational institutions have realised the growing benefits of online discussion to the extent that some are beginning to make it mandatory for students and teachers to participate in e-learning platforms in the school as a way to improve digital literacy skills. However, the finding disagrees with Dube et al. (2016) that ODF have been deployed to complement traditional learning techniques such as lectures and tutorials (Dube et al., 2016) as this finding has exposed that although, LIS students used some types of online discussion forum (ODF), other types are not so utilised. It was found in the course of research question two that the level of technical support provided to use online discussion forum among LIS students in selected Polytechnics in Nigeria was high since the weighted mean was a little above the criterion mean of 2.5. In other words, the result implies that technical support was adequately provided as institutional support for online discussion forum for LIS students with particular references to the provision of alternative power supply, adequate software and user friendly ODF platforms, among others. Similarly, the infrastructural support provided for online discussion forum by LIS students in selected Nigerian polytechnics was low especially in the areas of constant power supply within the campus, computer systems and

accessories and adequate Internet facilities within the campus for the use of students. Additionally, findings revealed that there was a moderate level of institutional support provided to use online discussion forum among LIS students in selected polytechnics in Nigeria but with a deficit in the level of infrastructural support. This could be due to the fact that the number of infrastructures provided for online discussion forum is far less than the number of students desirous of using the facilities. This explains the gross inadequacy of the infrastructural support for ODF among LIS students in Nigerian polytechnics.

The finding of this study corroborates Murali (2009) who stressed that learning mode requires a structured network at all its operational nodes and interconnected to each other, through a dedicated network so that all student services can be easily accessed by all operational nodes. Also, the finding lends credence to the tenacity of the assertion by Ratna (2018) that the extent to which universities provide support, assistance when needed, appreciation of contributions, care for social-emotional needs, well-being, relationships and feelings of mutual assistance among lecturers and leader describes the level of institutional support. In addition, the finding aligns with the previous studies by Ehiamentalor (2001) and Osagie (2003) that infrastructure can be viewed as the totality of all that goes into education such as classrooms, lecture theatres, laboratories, libraries, electricity, water, health centre, sports and recreation centres, ICT, machines and furniture put there-in, with the intention of facilitating teaching-learning.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. There is the need to create more awareness on various types of online discussion forums available for use as well as their usefulness among LIS students in Nigerian polytechnics.
2. LIS students in Nigerian polytechnics could be encouraged to use online discussion forums more frequently in order to complement the physical contacts periods and globalise learning. This could be achieved by sensitising them and making internet more accessible to students, functional electricity supply and more computers in the library for students' use.
3. There is the need for the implementation of institutional policies to support the use of online discussion forum for LIS students and lecturers for teaching, research and even conducting test and examinations which could be inform of institutional supports like technical support and infrastructure.

Suggestions for further studies

In view of the limitation encountered in the course of this study, the following areas are suggested for future research endeavours:

1. Influence of institutional support for online discussion forum use in Nigerian Universities rather than polytechnics.
2. The study of this nature could be carried out using students of other academic discipline apart from the LIS students in the polytechnics
3. Comparative study on institutional support for online discussion forum use by LIS students of public and private polytechnics in Nigeria.

Conclusion

The study explored the influence of institutional support, ICT competence and social influence on online discussion forum use among LIS students in selected Nigerian polytechnics. Online discussion forum use among LIS students was established to be influenced by institutional support. Consequently, it was established that institutional support is a significant predictors of online discussion forum use among LIS students in selected Nigerian polytechnics. It is therefore submitted that for online discussion forum to be optimally adopted and used by students in the polytechnics, there is the need for the government, the institutions, the staff and students to

harmonise the provision of this factor with a view to deploying it to fully support the implementation and use of online discussion forum.

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